

EFFECT OF 12-WEEK YOGIC THERAPY ON DIABETIC PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation was conducted to determine the effects of 12-week yogic therapy on diabetic patients. The respondents chosen for this study were divided into two groups at random. The pre and post-test random group design was used for analysis of the data. Thirty male diabetes patients were selected as a subject for the present investigation of Gwalior city. The patients were coffee bad on the basis of start period sampling when an advertisement was made that investigation is arranging a yogic camp for diabetic patients. All age of the subjects were ranging from 30-55 years. To investigate the influence, the 12-week yogic therapy was imparted to the subject of experimental "A" and control group "B". The groups were consisted of 15 subjects each. The 12-week of yogic therapy includes Poorna Bhujangasana, Dhanur asana, Baddhapadmasana, Kukkut asana and Hal asana. The pair t-test was used to identify the significant differences between the groups at the pre and post-tests data on diabetic patient. The significant values of critical difference at the selected level of 0.05. The obtain value of t-ratio was 8.587 which found the 12-week yogic therapy on diabetic patient was significant improvement at selected level.

Keywords: *Yogic Therapy, Blood Sugar Level, Diabetic Patients.*

INTRODUCTION

The technique of yoga has a long background. The prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (also referred to as *diabetes*) is increasing nationwide. From 1980 to 2005, prevalence of diabetes among the Indian population rose from 5.8 million to 14.7 million (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 1985). Approximately 9.6% of Indians aged 25 years or older (a total of 20.6 million people) have diabetes

(Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2005). Long-term complications such as blindness, end-stage renal disease, and lower extremity amputation are much higher among ethnic minorities than among non-Hispanic Whites with diabetes (American Diabetes Association, 2006). Healthcare professionals and policy makers agree that reducing racial and ethnic disparities in diabetes and other health-related outcomes is a national

priority; however, debate persists about root causes and taking appropriate action. Some argue that cultural practices are to blame, although culture itself is often defined poorly, if at all (Hunt, Schneider, Comer, 2004). Others purport that a viable solution is the promotion of cultural competence among healthcare providers (Betancourt, Green, Carrillo, Ananeh-Firempong O., 2003; Brach, 2000). Still others point to the lack of practical interventions tested among individuals with diabetes, particularly for the promotion of lifestyle changes in the form of physical activity (PA) and nutrition recommendations (King, Estabrooks, Strycker, Toobert, Bull, Glasgow, 2006; Kittler, Sucher, 2004). The implementation of yoga therapy varies widely. While many researchers conceptualize yoga as a form of PA, others argue that comprehensive yoga, an approach incorporating body postures (*asanas*), breathing techniques (*pranayamas*), meditation, cleansing, nutrition, attitudinal and behavioral modification, and mental discipline, is more beneficial and loyal to its ancient tenets (Manyam, 2004; Agte, Tarwadi, Sudarshan, 2004; Jain,

Uppal, Bhatnagar, Talukdar, 1993). Nonetheless, western forms of yoga primarily emphasize components of exercise and stress management (Frishman, Weintraub, Micozzi, 2005; Manyam, 2004). Yoga therapy has been associated with a multitude of benefits and few adverse effects according to a recent systematic review of the effects of yoga on physiologic and clinical risk factors in adults with diabetes (Innes, Vincent, 2007). Benefits include significant reductions in fasting and postprandial blood glucose levels, hemoglobin A_{1c}, total cholesterol and low-density lipoprotein, triglycerides, coronary stenosis, oxidative stress, blood pressure, body weight, waist-to-hip ratio, heart rate, catecholamine levels, need for medication relative to baseline, and psychosocial risk factors (Frishman, Weintraub, Micozzi, 2005; Innes, Vincent, 2007). Yoga is also associated with decreased weight gain in healthy adults, a matter of significance in the prevention and management of many chronic illnesses, including diabetes (Kristal, Littman, Benitez, 2005). Although intervention studies reveal similar positive findings,

many have a poor study design, lack an adequate control group, and offer an insufficient description of sampling and statistical analysis techniques (Innes, 2007).

Yoga-based therapy is clearly a promising intervention for primary and secondary prevention of diabetes, given the multiple health benefits attributed to the practice of yoga. However, the literature is unclear regarding the most beneficial forms of yoga, the possibility of a dose response relationship in managing diabetes, and the most labor-effective, cost-effective, and time-effective manner in which to train patients

METHODS

Subjects and Design

Thirty subjects were randomly selected from Gwalior. The diabetic patients were coffee bad on the basis of start period sampling when an advertisement was made that investigation is arranging a yogic camp for diabetic patient. All age of the subjects were ranging from 30-55 years. To investigate the influence, the 12-week yogics therapy was imparted to the subject of experimental "A" and control group "B". The groups were consisted of 15 subjects each. The

12-week of yogic therapy includes Poorna Bhujangasana, Dhanur asana, *Baddhapadmasana*, Kukkut asana and Hal asana. To purpose of present study is to determine the effects of 12-week yogic therapy on diabetic patients, Accu-check active blood glucometer used to record the amount of sugar present in the blood of the subjects.

To undertake this checkup Accu-check active test strips, Softclix lancing device and Lancets for lancets for virtually pain-free blood collector is used.

Procedure of test

Accu-check Active blood glucose meter used to record the amount of sugar level present in blood of the subjects in the morning with empty stomach as follow: Inserted the test strip and on the meter switched pick to get a drop of blood and place it on the test strip. After the five second note reading display by the instrument on the monitor. This way all 30 subjects blood sugar was tested and reading was noted for the record. Accu-check active blood glucometer was used to record the amount of sugar present in the blood for pre and post-test of the subjects.

12-Week of Yogic Therapy Programme

The students went through yogic therapy (for 12-week) through training programme under strict supervision of the researcher. Experimental group practiced following asana for therapy during the training:

1. Poorna Bhujangasana
2. Dhanur asana
3. *Baddhapadmasana*
4. Kukkut asana
5. Hal asana

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The pair t-test was used to identify the significant differences between the groups at the pre and post-tests data for sugar level present in blood of diabetic patient. The significant values of critical difference at the selected level of 0.05.

HYPOTHESIS

It was hypothesized that there may not be significant difference in the effect of 12-week yogic therapy on diabetic patient.

Inference

Since, the results have shown significant differences in the effect of 12-week yogic therapy on sugar level in blood of the diabetic patient. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected at the selected level of significance.

RESULTS

In order to compare the pre and post-test means of all the experimental groups and control group, the 't' ratios (Verma, 2000) were calculated, the results are given in tables 1 & 2.

TABLE 1 Comparison of mean values between pre and post-test of the Blood sugar level of the experiment group

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	234.5333	127.6667
95% CI for the mean	208.56 to 260.49	119.266 to 136.06
Variance	2198.2667	230.0952
Standard deviation	46.8857	15.1689
Standard error of the mean	12.1058	3.9166
Paired samples t-Mean difference	-106.8667	
Standard deviation	48.2018	
95% CI	-133.5599 to -80.1734	
Test statistic t	8.587	
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14	
Two-tailed probability	P < 0.0001	

TABLE 2 Comparison of mean values between pre and post-test of the Blood sugar level of the control group

	Pre-Test	Post-Test
Sample size	15	15
Arithmetic mean	232.8667	233.8667
95% CI for the mean	196.814 to 268.918	197.904 to 269.828
Variance	4238.2667	4217.1238
Standard deviation	65.1020	64.9394
Standard error of the mean	16.8093	16.7673
Paired samples t-Mean difference	1.0000	
Standard deviation	14.4123	
95% CI	-6.9813 to 8.9813	
Test statistic t	0.269	
Degrees of Freedom (DF)	14	
Two-tailed probability	P = 0.7921	

TABLE 3 Comparison of mean values between pre and post test of the Blood sugar level of the experiment group and control Group

Group	Experimental (Pre-test)	Experimental (Post-test)	Control (Pre-test)	Control (Post-test)
Number	15	15	15	15
Mean	234.5	127.6	232.8	233.8
S.D	46.88	15.16	65.10	64.93
SEM	12.10	3.91	0.166	0.167
't' Value	8.587		0.269	

As shown in Table-3 that the value of pre-test of experimental group and post-test of experimental group mean was 234.5 and 127.6 respectively. Whereas the value of pre-test of control group and post-test of control group mean was 232.8 and 233.8. The obtained value of t-ratio was 8.587 which were found significant at selected level. Therefore, the hypothesis is rejected at the selected level of significance. The line graph showing the effect of 12-week yogic therapy on blood sugar level of experimental and control group in figure1.

FIGURE 1 Line graph showing Mean, Standard Error of Mean (SEM), Standard Deviation (SD) of blood sugar level of experimental and control group

FIGURE 2 Probability values of a T-test of experimental group of Sugar level in blood

FIGURE 3 Probability values of a T-test of control group of Sugar level in blood

DISCUSSION

The result of the study confirms the notion that any yogic therapy particularly effective on sugar level in blood, when administered according to the set principles of 12-week yogic therapy in progressive manner on diabetic patients. The findings of this study are in consonance with the results of the study done by P. Ananda Kumar an investigation to find out the effect of selected asana and suryanamaskar on test namely resting pulse rate and respiratory rate among

diabetic patients. The study revealed that the criterion variables were significantly improved due to the influence of asana and suryana-maskar on resting pulse rate and respiratory rate among diabetic patients. Blood sugar levels are controlled by a complex interaction of multiple chemicals and hormones in the body, including the hormone insulin made in the beta cells of the pancreas by Rother. Through the adoption of yogic therapy sufficient insulin is produced

and functions correctly. The amount of glucose in the bloodstream is normal and ability to store the glucose which helps the subject resulting in maintaining normal sugar level on diabetic patient. The results have shown significant differences in the effect of 12-week yogic therapy on sugar level in blood of the diabetic patient.

CONCLUSIONS

Within the limitations and delimitations set for the present study and considering the results obtained, the conclusions were drawn: The sugar level in blood was significantly decreased due to 12-week weeks of yogic therapy on diabetic patients.

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